

MAGNIFICATION AND FRACTION GRACEFUL LABELING

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ABSTRACT. For a (p, q) graph $G(V, E)$ with the labeling set of vertices and edges are A and B respectively. In this paper, the vertex set and edge set of G are labeled by lA and lB respectively, where $l \in \mathbb{N}$. We establish the relation between graphs labeled by sets A, B and lA, lB under certain conditions.

Keywords: Graceful labeling, l -Magnification graceful, odd graceful, prime graceful labeling, fraction graceful, α -fraction graceful.

Mathematics Subject Classification: 05C78

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of graceful labeling was first given by Rosa [9] in 1967. Graceful labeling is an injective assignment of the positive integers of the vertices of a (p, q) -graph G from 0 to q and the edge is labeled bijectively by the modulus difference of the end vertices of the edges from 1 to q . Rosa [9] proved that path, caterpillar and cycle C_n can be labeled gracefully when $n \equiv 0, 3 \pmod{4}$.

Acharya and Hegde [1] define f is injective assignment of vertex set to the $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, k + (q - 1)d\}$ and induced mapping $f^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{k, k + d, \dots, k + (q - 1)d\}$ is bijective. Then f is called (k, d) graceful labeling, Where f^* is the modulus difference of end vertices of each edge. Gnanajothi [4] introduced odd graceful labeling in 1991, vertex and edge label defined in the set $\{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, (2q - 1)\}$ and $\{1, 3, 5, \dots, (2q - 1)\}$ respectively. She proved that $P_n, C_n, K_{m,n}, P_n \odot K_1$ and crown $C_n \odot K_1$ for $n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$ are odd graceful and conjectured that tree graph are always odd graceful. Barrientos [2] proved that if all components of a forest are caterpillars, then it is odd graceful and a tree of maximum diameter five is odd graceful and conjectured that all bipartite graphs are odd graceful. Neela and Selvaraj [7] prove that the finite union of stars, paths and caterpillar, finite unions of ladders, the finite union of bi-star, paths and caterpillar, Corona graph $K_{m,n} \odot rK_1$ all are odd graceful. Gao [5] proved that the union of the finite number of paths, the union of the finite number of stars, the union of any number of paths and stars, $C_m \cup P_n, C_m \cup C_n$ and union of any number of cycles divided by 4 is odd graceful.

A. Tout et al. [11] introduced prime labeling. Prime labeling is defined as vertex set to $\{0, 1, 2, \dots, p\}$ is injective and for each edge adjacent vertices should be co-prime. Path graph P_n , star graph $K_{1,n}$, cycle C_n , friendship graph $F_n, K_{m,2} \cup P_n$, bistar $B_{m,n}, C_4 \cup P_n$ and

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$K_{m,2}$ are prime graceful [10]. Entringer [8] conjectured that all tree graphs are always prime graceful. Haxell et al. [6] proved that the large tree is prime graceful. Moreover, one can see the excellent survey of graph labeling by Gallian [3].

2. RESULTS

Graceful Labeling: Fraction and Magnification

Definition 2.1. The function $h : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, \frac{1}{q}, \frac{2}{q}, \dots, \frac{q}{q} = 1\}$ is one-one mapping and induced function $h^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{\frac{1}{q}, \frac{2}{q}, \dots, \frac{q}{q} = 1\}$ is defined as $h^*(xy) = |h(x) - h(y)| \forall$ edge $xy = e \in E$ is bijective mapping. Then h is called fraction graceful labeling on G .

Definition 2.2. If h is fraction graceful labeling on G and $\exists r \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $h(x) \leq \frac{r}{q} < h(y)$ or $h(y) \leq \frac{r}{q} < h(x) \forall$ edge $xy = e \in E$, then h is called α -fraction graceful labeling on G .

Definition 2.3. The function $h : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, l, 2l, \dots, ql\}$ (where $l \in \mathbb{N}$) is one-one mapping and induced function $h^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{l, 2l, \dots, ql\}$ is defined as $h^*(xy) = |h(x) - h(y)| \forall$ edge $xy = e \in E$ is bijective mapping. Then h is called l -magnification graceful labeling.

Definition 2.4. If h is l -magnification graceful labeling on G and $\exists r \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $h(x) \leq lr < h(y)$ or $h(y) \leq lr < h(x) \forall$ edge $xy = e \in E$. Then h is called l -magnification- α -graceful labeling on G .

Definition 2.5. The function $h : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, l, 2l, \dots, l(k + (q - 1)d)\}$ (where $k, d \in \mathbb{N}$) is one-one mapping and induced function $h^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{lk, l(k + d), \dots, l(k + (q - 1)d)\}$ is defined as $h^*(xy) = |h(x) - h(y)| \forall$ edge $xy = e \in E$ is bijective. Then h is called l -magnification- (k, d) -graceful labeling on G .

Theorem 2.6. h is graceful labeling on graph G if and only if h is l -magnification graceful labeling on graph G .

Proof. Define $g : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, l, 2l, \dots, ql\}$ such that $g(x) = lh(x) \forall x \in V$. If $g(x_1) = g(x_2) \forall x_1, x_2 \in V \implies h(x_1) = h(x_2)$. Since h is graceful on $G \implies g$ is injective. Define induced mapping $g^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{l, 2l, \dots, ql\}$ such that $g^*(xy) = |g(x) - g(y)| \forall e = xy \in E$. $g^*(xy) = l|h(x) - h(y)| \implies g^*(xy) = lh^*(xy)$ (where h^* is induced mapping of h). Since h^* is bijective therefore g^* is bijective. Hence h is l -magnification graceful labeling.

Converse: putting $l = 1$. □

Corollary 2.7. h is graceful labeling on G if and only if h is fraction graceful labeling on G .

Proof. putting $l = 1/q$ in Theorem 2.6 □

Theorem 2.8. h is α -graceful labeling on G if and only if h is l -magnification- α -graceful labeling on G .

Proof. Define $g : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, l, 2l, \dots, ql\}$ such that $g(x) = lh(x) \forall x \in V$. h is α -graceful labeling on G . So $\exists r \in \mathbb{N}$ and two disjoint set C and D such that $C \cup D = V \implies$ for any edge $xy = e \in E(G)$, $x \in C, y \in D$ such that $h(x) \leq r < h(y)$ or $h(y) \leq r < h(x)$. If we multiply by l then inequality becomes $g(x) \leq lr < g(y)$ or $g(y) \leq lr < g(x)$. Hence h is l -magnification α -graceful labeling on G .

Converse: Putting $l = 1$. □

Corollary 2.9. *h is α -graceful labeling on G if and only if h is α -fraction graceful labeling on G .*

Proof. Putting $l = 1/q$ in Theorem 2.8 □

Theorem 2.10. *h is (k, d) -graceful labeling on graph G if and only if h is l -magnification- (k, d) -graceful labeling on graph G , where $k, d \in \mathbb{N}, l > 0$*

Proof. Define $g : V \rightarrow \{0, l, 2l, 3l, \dots, l(k + (q - 1)d)\}$ such that $g(x) = lh(x)$. Since h is injective. So g is injective. Define induced mapping $g^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{lk, l(k + d), l(k + 2d), \dots, l(k + (q - 1)d)\}$ such that \forall edge $e = xy \in E, g^*(xy) = |g(x) - g(y)|$. $g^*(xy) = lh^*(xy)$ where h^* is induced mapping of h . Since h^* is bijective. So g^* is bijective. Hence h is l -magnification- (k, d) -graceful labeling.

Converse putting $l = 1$. □

Theorem 2.11. *h is (k, d) -graceful labeling on G if and only if h is l -magnification- (k, d) -graceful labeling on G , where $k, d \in \mathbb{N}$.*

Proof. Define $g : V \rightarrow \{0, l, 2l, \dots, l(k + (q - 1)d)\}$ such that $g(x) = lh(x)$. Since h is injective. So g is injective. Define induced mapping $g^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{lk, l(k + d), l(k + 2d), \dots, l(k + (q - 1)d)\}$ such that \forall edge $xy = e \in E, g^*(xy) = |g(x) - g(y)|$. $g^*(xy) = lh^*(xy)$ where h^* is induced mapping of h . Since h^* is bijective. So g^* is bijective. Hence h is l -magnification- (k, d) -graceful labeling.

Converse putting $l = 1$. □

Odd Graceful Labeling: Fraction and Magnification

Definition 2.12. *The function $h : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, \frac{1}{q}, \frac{2}{q}, \dots, \frac{(2q-1)}{q}\}$ is one-one mapping and induced function $h^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{\frac{1}{q}, \frac{3}{q}, \dots, \frac{(2q-1)}{q}\}$ is defined as $f^*(xy) = |f(x) - f(y)| \forall$ edge $xy = e \in E(G)$ is bijective. Then h is called odd fraction graceful labeling on G .*

Definition 2.13. *The function $h : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, l, 2l, \dots, (2q - 1)l\}$ is one-one mapping and induced function $h^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{l, 3l, \dots, (2q - 1)l\}$ is defined as $h^*(xy) = |h(x) - h(y)| \forall$ edge $xy = e \in E(G)$ is bijective. Then h is called l -magnification odd graceful labeling on G .*

Theorem 2.14. *h is odd graceful labeling on graph G if and only if f is l -magnification odd-graceful labeling on G .*

Proof. Define $g : V(G) \rightarrow \{0, l, 2l, \dots, (2q - 1)l\}$ such that $g(x) = lh(x) \forall x \in V(G)$. $g(x_1) = g(x_2) \implies h(x_1) = h(x_2)$. Since h is injective. So g is injective. Define induced mapping $g^* : E(G) \rightarrow \{l, 3l, \dots, (2q - 1)l\}$ such that $g^*(xy) = |g(x) - g(y)| \forall$ edge $xy = e \in E(G) \implies g^*(xy = e) = lh^*(xy = e)$. g^* is bijective because h^* is bijective. Hence h is l -magnification odd graceful.

Converse: Putting $l = 1$. □

Corollary 2.15. *h is odd-graceful labeling on G if and only if h is odd-fraction graceful labeling on G .*

Proof. Putting: $l = 1/q$ in Theorem 2.14. □

Prime labeling: Fraction and Magnification

Definition 2.16. *The function $h : V(G) \rightarrow \{l, 2l, \dots, pl\}$ is bijective and \forall edge $xy = e \in E(G), \gcd(h(x), h(y)) = l$. Then h is called l -magnification prime labeling on G .*

Definition 2.17. *The function $h : V(G) \longrightarrow \{lk, l(k+d), \dots, l(k+(p-1)d)\}$ (where $k, d \in \mathbb{N}$) is injective and \forall edge $xy = e \in E(G)$ such that $\gcd(h(x), h(y)) = l$. Then h is called l -magnification- (k, d) -prime labeling on G .*

Theorem 2.18. *h is prime labeling on G if and only if h is l -magnification prime labeling on G .*

Proof. Define $g : V(G) \longrightarrow \{l, 2l, \dots, pl\}$ such that $g(x) = lh(x) \forall x \in V(G)$. $g(x_1) = g(x_2) \implies h(x_1) = h(x_2)$. Since h is injective. So g is injective. For \forall edge $xy = e \in E$, $\gcd(g(x), g(y)) = \gcd(lh(x), lh(y)) = l \gcd(h(x), h(y))$. Since h is prime labeling. So $\gcd(h(x), h(y)) = 1$. Hence h is l -magnification prime labeling.

Converse: Putting $l = 1$. □

Theorem 2.19. *h is (k, d) -prime labeling on G if and if h is l -magnification- (k, d) -prime labeling on G , where $k, d \in \mathbb{N}$.*

Proof. Prove as similar to the Theorem 2.18 □

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